

Effects Of Explicit And Implicit Instructional Strategies On Colleges Of Education Students' Morphology Competence In The Structure Of English In Osun State, Nigeria

Beatrice Bunmi Adeyemi, PhD

General and Entrepreneurial Studies Unit

Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology (OAUSTECH),
Okitipupa, Ondo State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of three strategies (i.e. explicit, implicit and conventional instructional strategies) on Private Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in Osun State. The study also assessed the interaction effect of explicit, implicit and conventional instructional strategies on Private Colleges of Education students' morphology competence based on gender in the study area. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group quasi-experimental design with a 3x2 factorial matrix. The population consisted of approved Private Colleges of Education in Osun State. Simple random sampling was employed in selecting three Private Colleges of Education out of the approved ones. The sample size consisted of 115 students of 200 level of English in their intact classes in the three Colleges. The 200 level English students were assigned randomly to two experimental groups (Explicit and implicit instructional strategies) and one control group (conventional strategy). An instrument titled: Morphology Competence Test (MCT) was used to collect data for the study. Data collected were analysed using frequency, percentage, standard deviation, mean and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The results showed that there was significant effect of explicit and implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in Osun State ($F = 8.374$; $p < 0.05$). Whereas, there was no significant interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area ($F = 1.191$; $p > 0.05$). The study concluded that explicit instructional strategy had a significant effect on Colleges of Education students' competence in Morphology aspect of Structure of English in Osun State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Morphology Competence, Implicit Strategies, Explicit Strategies, Conventional Strategies

INTRODUCTION

English is the official language and the means of disseminating knowledge at all stages of education. It is the lingua franca bridging the gap between the country's diverse indigenous languages and serving as an essential tool for interethnic and international. Using English effectively is essential for academic development, societal attainment, and connection with other nations. Adeyemi (1) opine that English is widely learnt as a second language and parents want their wards to be knowledgeable in it. This, of course, requires adequate mastery of grammatical structures for constructing and comprehending needed information. Morphology is a sub-discipline of linguistics that is concerned with the internal structure of words. It provides the grammatical structure needed for storing information, transmitting, and interpreting ideas. Morphology refers to the study of the structure and formation of words, including morphemes - the smallest units of meaning [2]. In morphology, proficient learners are better able to understand new words, create new forms, and use language more precisely and imaginatively. Because of this, it is essential for acquiring more general language skills like writing, reading, and vocabulary

growth. Carlisle (3) indicates that for learners of English as a second language, developing morphological awareness is significant to enhancing vocabulary, reading comprehension, and syntactic development.

Despite the benefits derive from learning morphology, it is frequently disregarded when teaching English in Nigerian educational institutions. It is expected of these institutions, who hold the responsibility of training future teachers, to produce graduates who demonstrate both the pedagogical competence and solid grammatical proficiency needed to successfully teach English. This necessitates the need to use the appropriate instructional strategies to teach. Explicit instruction is characterized by direct teaching of rules, concepts, and patterns. It involves conscious learning where teachers explain morphological rules and guide students through structured practice. Implicit instruction, on the other hand, involves a more inductive approach. Learners are exposed to linguistic forms in context and are expected to acquire knowledge through usage, repetition, and exposure rather than direct explanation [4]. In Nigeria, where English is a second language and students

often come from diverse linguistic backgrounds, explicit instruction provides the needed clarity and scaffolding for mastering morphological structures [5].

Unfortunately, repetitive memorization, decontextualized rule listing, and minimal participation by students are prominent characteristics of morphology pedagogy. Effective learning and long-term retention are impaired by conventional teaching methods, which primarily rely on teacher-focused methodologies and reduce morphology to a set of abstract concepts. Arnoff (2) state that any morphological concepts such as allomorphy, zero morphemes, and derivational processes are not easily observable, making it difficult for students to grasp them through rote learning or deductive instruction, which are hallmarks of traditional teaching strategies.

The persistent poor performance of Nigerian potential teachers in the grammatical components of English is essentially disturbing. Academic performance assessments and national evaluations frequently highlighted poor results in areas including word formation, affixation, derivation, and inflection. Since many of the students are likely to imitate the unsuccessful teaching approaches they were taught, these deficiencies not only indicate inadequacies in the students' own language fluency but also portend challenges in their future practices in the classroom. This study examines the impact of three teaching strategies: explicit, implicit, and conventional on enhancing morphology competency among students in a subset of private Colleges of Education in Osun State, Nigeria, in response to these pedagogical limitations. Though their designs and cognitive demands are very different, both strategies have bases in contemporary theories on second language acquisition. Studies have shown that learners exposed to rich morphological input over time tend to develop greater automaticity in word formation and usage [6].

The requirement to objectively assess which of these teaching strategies fosters greater morphological comprehension and enhanced achievement among prospective instructors serves as the foundation for this investigation. Acknowledging that cognitive and affective differences may have an impact on learning outcomes, it additionally seeks to examine the potential interaction effects of gender on students' reactions to each instructional strategy. The rationale for examining gender as a variable in this study stems from the broader discourse on equity and inclusiveness in education. In many educational contexts, gender stereotypes and assumptions have historically influenced perceptions of teaching competence and performance [7].

The study's focus on private Colleges of Education in Osun State adds an essential regional dimension to the discussion about the teaching of languages in Nigeria. These educational institutions make up an increasing percentage of the teacher education landscape as they frequently operate under different administrative and instructional models than public colleges. By looking into how their students react to various teaching strategies, the results of this research can help shape more comprehensive modifications in English language instruction nationwide. In the long run, the study's findings are expected to enhance teacher education's use of English language pedagogy, pre-service teachers' grammatical proficiency, and the general standard of English instruction in Nigerian classrooms.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Most of the studies carried out in Nigeria, especially experimental studies are limited to primary and secondary levels of education. English as a course of study is studied at all levels of education. This particular study is in Colleges of Education where English is taught as a specialized subject. Morphology is a subset of ENG 211 – The Structure of English that entails morphology, syntax and semantics. However, the lecturer handling the course must be versatile in diverse teaching strategies from the conventional strategy which places emphasis on chalk and talk approach to facilitate full understanding of the topic as well as the ability to regurgitate information they have learned and equally for better performance. This study therefore intends to investigate the effect of three teaching strategies (Explicit, Implicit and Conventional) on Colleges of Education students' competence in morphology aspect of the structure of English. Gender was incorporated into the study as intervening variable.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to investigate the effect of Explicit and Implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education Students' morphology competence in the structure of English in Osun State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- (1) investigate the effect of Explicit and Implicit Instructional Strategies on Colleges of Education Students' morphology competence in the structure of English in Osun State, Nigeria; and
- (2) assess the interactive effect of Explicit and Implicit instructional strategies and sex on College of Education students' morphology competence in the study area.

HYPOTHESES

In line with the objectives of the study, the following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant.

Ho1 There is no significant effect of explicit and implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the structure of English in Osun State, Nigeria.

Ho2 There is no significant interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' competence in the structure of English in the study area.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Morphology which deals with the structure and construction of words, is the primary component of language that affects vocabulary development, grammatical precision, and overall language ability. The study provides important insights that might direct pedagogically practices in Colleges of Education by examining the effects of various instructional strategies—specifically, explicit, implicit, and conventional instructional strategies — on students' competency in this area. The potential of this research to enhance morphology instruction and learning in the Nigerian context is one of its main contributions. The study determines which teaching method improves students' comprehension of morphological structures using empirical analysis. This directly affects implementing the curriculum, teaching efficacy, and the creation of educational resources appropriate for Nigerian students' learning goals.

Furthermore, the study's recommendations are helpful to English language teachers since they provide practical approaches for raising students' morphological proficiency. Teachers may improve their instructional delivery and ensure better learning results for their students through using research-backed strategies that have been proven to be beneficial. Moreover, the research contributes to the current corpus of knowledge in language learning and applied linguistics, specifically in the field of instructional strategies for teaching language structure. This study covers a significant vacuum in the literature by providing contextually and culturally relevant data that can guide educational practices and policies, particularly in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

The study's contribution to students' communicative competence is another significant aspect of its importance. Words are the building elements of language, and their formation and interpretation require morphological expertise. Since students in Colleges of Education are being prepared to become future teachers, the study emphasizes the need to adopt instructional strategies that can strengthen their linguistic foundation. This will ensure the recruitment and retention of qualified and competent English language teachers who can effectively train future generations of learners.

Finally, the study has implications for teacher education policy and practice. Improving this competence will not only improve students' written and spoken English but also offer the language skills needed for academic success and effective communication in both professional and social contexts.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group quasi-experimental design with a 3x2 factorial matrix (three treatment groups – Explicit Instructional Strategy group, Implicit Instructional Strategy group and Control group and two gender groups – male and female). The population of the study consisted of all 200 level from English Department of Approved Private Colleges of Education in Osun State. Simple random sampling technique was employed in selecting three Private Colleges of Education in Osun State out of the four approved private Colleges of Education in the State. The sample used for the study consisted of 115 students from English Department in the selected and approved Private Colleges of Education in Osun State (Assanusiya College of Education, Ode Omu (40), Grace College of Education, Osogbo (38), and Ilori College of Education, Ede (37). In each College, an intact class of 200 level of English students were used. The three Colleges were randomly assigned to two experimental groups and one control group respectively.

Students in the experimental group were taught morphology aspect of the structure of English which is ENG 211 as approved by National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) using Explicit Instructional Strategy for Assanusiya College of Education, Ode Omu (40) based on the Explicit Instructional Guide (EIG) designed for the topic, Implicit Instructional Strategy was made up for Grace College of Education, Osogbo (38) based on the Implicit Instructional Guide (IIG) designed for the topic while students in the control group (Ilori College of Education, Ede (37) were taught using Conventional Instructional Strategy (CIS).

An Instrument tagged “Morphology Competence Test (MCT)” was used to collect data for the study. The MCT was used to determine the students' competence in morphology aspect of the Structure of English. It has two sections; Section A contained concise demographic information of the respondents while Section B contained twenty-five (25) multiple objective tests on morphology competence. The result of the reliability test conducted for MCT yielded a Kuder Richardson – value of 0.79. Three Research Assistants were properly trained on the use of the Instructional Guides as well as the use of the instrument, appropriate permission was sought from the Provosts of the three Colleges of Education, six

weeks were spent in the administration of the instrument. Data collected were analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean standard deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

RESULTS

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant effect of explicit and implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education students’ morphology competence in Osun State.

In order to test this hypothesis, data collected on the morphology competence of Colleges of Education students having been taught with Explicit Instructional Strategies (EIS), Implicit Instructional Strategies (IIS) and Conventional Strategy (CS) were subjected to descriptive analysis, analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and Scheffe post-hoc analysis statistical tools using posttest scores as dependent variable, pretest scores as covariate and the strategies as independent variables. The results are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of the effects of explicit and implicit instruction guides on Colleges of Education students’ pragmatic competence in Osun State

S/N	Instruction Guides	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
1.	EIS	40	20.06	1.87
2.	IIS	38	19.18	1.74
3.	CS	37	18.49	1.64
Total		115	19.27	1.86

N = 115

Results in Table 1 showed the descriptive analysis of the effect of explicit and implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education students’ pragmatic competence in Osun State. It can be deduced from the Table that students exposed to the EIS, IIS and CS had posttest mean scores of (\bar{x} =

20.06), (\bar{x} = 19.18 and (\bar{x} = 18.49) respectively. Table 2 shows the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the effect of explicit and implicit instructional Strategies on Colleges of Education students’ morphology competence in Osun State.

Table 2: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the effect of explicit and implicit instructional Strategies on Colleges of Education students’ morphology competence in Osun State

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects
Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Squares	Sum of df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	55.562 ^a	3	18.521	6.063	.001	.141	
Intercept	701.477	1	701.477	229.632	.000	.674	
Pretest	6.647	1	6.647	2.176	.143	.019	
Strategies	51.162	2	25.581	8.374	.000	.531	
Error	339.082	111	3.055				
Total	43096.000	115					
Corrected Total	394.643	114					

R Squared = .141 (Adjusted R Squared = .118)

Results in Table 2 showed that there was significant effect of explicit and implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education students’ morphology competence in Osun State ($F = 8.374$; $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant effect of explicit and implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education students’ morphology competence in Osun State is hereby rejected. The partial eta squared value of 0.531 accounted for 53.1% effect size of explicit and implicit instructional strategies on Colleges of Education students’ morphology competence in Osun State. Table 3 shows the Scheffe post-hoc analysis of the difference in the morphology competence of the Colleges of Education students taught using explicit and implicit instructional strategies in Osun State.

Results in Table 3 showed the scheffe post-hoc analysis of the difference in the morphology competence of Colleges of Education students taught using explicit and implicit instructional strategies in Osun State. It can be observed from the Table that the morphology competence of Colleges of Education students taught using explicit instructional strategies were significantly different from those taught using conventional strategy (Mean Difference = 1.5885; $p < 0.05$); however, morphology competence of Colleges of Education students taught using explicit instructional strategy were significantly not different from those taught using implicit instructional strategy (Mean Difference = .8908; $p > 0.05$) and that the morphology competence of Colleges of Education students taught using explicit instructional strategy were significantly not different from those taught using conventional strategy (Mean Difference = .6977; $p > 0.05$) in Osun State.

Table 3: Scheffe post-hoc analysis of differences in the morphology competence of Colleges of Education students taught using explicit and implicit instructional strategies in Osun State

Multiple Comparisons							
Dependent Variable: Posttest scores							
(I) Strategies	(J) Strategies	Scheffe			95% Confidence Interval		
		Mean (I-J)	Difference	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
EIS	IIS	.8908*		.39800	.086	-.0966	1.8782
	CS	1.5885*		.40075	.001	.5943	2.5827
IIS	EIS	-.8908*		.39800	.086	-1.8782	.0966
	CS	.6977*		.40579	.232	-.3090	1.7044
CS	EIS	-1.5885*		.40075	.001	-2.5827	-.5943
	IIS	-.6977*		.40579	.232	-1.7049	.3090

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square (Error) = 3.040.

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area.

Instructional Strategy (EIS), Implicit Instructional Strategy (IIS) and Conventional Strategy (CS) based on sex were subjected to descriptive analysis and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) statistical tools using posttest scores as dependent variable, pretest scores as covariate and the strategies as independent variables. The results are presented in Tables 4 and 5 respectively

In order to test this hypothesis, data collected on the morphology competence of the students in Colleges of Education having been taught with Explicit

Table 4: Descriptive analysis of the interaction effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area

S/N	Strategies	Sex	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
1.	EIS	Male	19	20.42	1.95
		Female	21	19.76	1.78
		Total	40	20.08	1.87
2.	IIS	Male	18	19.72	1.52
		Female	20	18.70	1.81
		Total	38	19.18	1.74
3.	CS	Male	18	18.39	1.58
		Female	19	18.58	1.74
		Total	37	18.49	1.64
Total		Male	55	19.53	1.87
		Female	60	19.03	1.83
		Total	115	19.27	1.86

N = 115

Results in Table 4 showed the descriptive analysis of the interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area. Considering total mean values of the students having been exposed to the instructional strategies, it can be gathered from the Table that male students had a

mean score of ($\bar{x} = 19.53$) while the female students have a mean score of ($\bar{x} = 19.27$) indicating no difference in their morphology competence. Table 5 shows the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area.

Table 5: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	63.482 ^a	5	12.696	4.179	.002	.161
Intercept	42539.511	1	42539.511	14001.645	.000	.992
Strategies	49.884	2	24.942	8.210	.000	.131
Sex	7.083	1	7.083	2.331	.130	.021
Strategies * Sex	7.237	2	3.618	1.191	.308	.021
Error	331.162	109	3.038			
Total	43096.000	115				
Corrected Total	394.643	114				

R Squared = .161 (Adjusted R Squared = .122)

(F = 1.191; p > 0.05)

Results in Table 5 showed that there was no significant interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area ($F = 1.191$; $p > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant interactive effect of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area is hereby not rejected. The partial eta squared value of 0.021 accounted for insignificant 2.1% interactive effect size of the two instructional strategies and sex on Colleges of Education students' morphology competence in the study area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study underscore the significant role those instructional strategies - particularly explicit, implicit and conventional strategies play in enhancing students' competence in English morphology. The comparative analysis revealed that students exposed to explicit instructional strategies performed significantly better than their counterparts taught using implicit and conventional strategies. This outcome aligns with a growing body of international and local literature that has highlighted the advantages of structured, conscious language teaching. Norris (8) offer foundational support for this study's findings through their comprehensive meta-analysis. They evaluated multiple studies on the effectiveness of form-focused instruction and concluded that explicit instruction consistently yields greater accuracy in language learning. Their analysis reinforces the observed effectiveness of structured morphological instruction in the current study, especially among adult learners in tertiary institutions who benefit from clear rules and direct feedback.

Similarly, Jeon (9) provided empirical evidence on the impact of instructional approaches on pragmatic competence, affirming that explicit instruction fosters better performance in targeted linguistic features. In the context of this study, the rules-based nature of morphology, such as affixation, compounding, and derivation, appears to lend itself more readily to the explicit method, where rules and patterns are taught deliberately and reinforced systematically. Olagbaju (10), for instance, investigated the impact of explicit and generative instructional strategies on students' achievements in summary writing in Ibadan. His findings demonstrated that students taught using explicit strategies outperformed those exposed to more implicit, discovery-based approaches. This directly supports the present study's outcome that explicit instruction in morphology enhances not only comprehension but also the productive application of word formation skills in structured English.

Don-Ezenne (11) also documented similar results in a different but relevant linguistic area, reading fluency. Her study on primary school pupils in Plateau State

showed that explicit instruction significantly enhanced pupils' reading fluency, a skill closely tied to morphological awareness. Fluency, in turn, is a predictor of overall language competence, thus reaffirming that explicit methods provide a strong foundation for language learning across age groups and educational levels. Within the context of English Language education in Osun State, Adeyemi (12) explored the significance of teacher-student relationships in determining academic performance. While their focus was on interpersonal dynamics, their research indirectly supports the current study by suggesting that instructional delivery methods, including clarity, structure, and feedback are central to academic success. Their findings reinforce the idea that students benefit more from a learning environment where instruction is methodical and explicitly focused on learning objectives.

Further validation comes from Adeyemi (1), whose comparative study of students' performance in English and Social Studies pointed to the necessity of context-specific and subject-sensitive pedagogical approaches. They concluded that the underperformance in English could be attributed to ineffective instructional strategies, hence the need for teacher training in methods such as the explicit approach used in this study. In contrast, students exposed to implicit instruction, while showing some improvement, lagged behind their explicitly taught peers. This supports Lopez's (13) findings in her comparative study of grammar acquisition, where explicit instruction produced more immediate and sustained learning outcomes than implicit exposure, particularly in formal educational contexts where assessment and competence demonstration are essential.

The study establishes that gender does not have any effect on the teaching of the morphological aspect of English. The findings align with previous research that suggests gender may not be a determining factor in the effectiveness of teaching technical linguistic content [14]. The teaching of morphology requires a clear comprehension of linguistic concepts, the capacity to present abstract grammatical structures in accessible forms, and the use of appropriate instructional strategies, competencies that are not inherently gendered.

Additionally, the study by Ogunjimi (15), which focused on guided inquiry and explicit instruction in Mathematics, reveals a parallel pattern. They found that students exposed to explicit methods achieved higher performance levels, demonstrating that structured instruction enhances comprehension in both language and numerical domains. Thus, the present study's findings are consistent with both global and local scholarship on the topic. They provide strong empirical backing for the adoption of

explicit instructional strategies in teaching morphology, particularly in Colleges of Education where future English Language teachers are trained. These findings not only validate the theoretical assertions of previous researchers but also contribute new insights to the practical implementation of effective pedagogy in Nigerian higher education.

CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE STUDY TO KNOWLEDGE

The study's main contribution is the expansion of knowledge in learning a second language, especially with reference to morphological development. It shows how students' comprehension of English morphological structure is influenced by explicit, implicit and traditional methods of teaching. The study adds to theoretical considerations in language learning by contrasting the efficacy of the three teaching modalities. In addition, the study influences instructional design and curriculum creation in teacher training colleges and other higher institution of learning. Its conclusions act as a roadmap for teachers and curriculum designers to embrace and include the best teaching strategies for raising college students' English language ability. This is particularly important in teacher education since the future of English language instruction in Nigerian schools is directly impacted by the caliber of training pre-service teachers get.

Another noteworthy contribution of the study is it emphasis on a particular geographic and educational context, Colleges of Education in Osun State, Nigeria. Context-sensitive data from this localization aids in comprehending the linguistic difficulties and educational requirements of Nigerian learners. By providing insights rooted in the Nigerian educational context, it closes a gap in the literature and aids in the creation of more successful teaching strategies that are culturally and linguistically appropriate.

The study greatly advances our understanding of curriculum development, teacher education, second language acquisition, and English language instruction. Teachers, academics, curriculum designers, and language policy makers in Nigeria and elsewhere might benefit from its theoretical and practical insights.

The study further reveals that gender does not significantly influence the teaching of the morphology aspect of English. The findings contribute to ongoing conversations about gender equity in education and affirm the potential of all teachers, regardless of gender, to deliver high-quality instruction in English morphology when given equal training and support.

Lastly, the paper establishes a framework for further investigation. It encourages more research into how

teaching methods affect students' long-term proficiency in the English language. On the basis of this work, future scholars might investigate other facets of language structure, such as syntax and phonology, or carry out comparative analyses in different states or geographical areas.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Explicit Instruction strategy should be integrated in Language Curriculum: It is important for Colleges of Education to include this approach significantly when teaching English morphology. This involves planned lessons on how words are formed, explaining rules, inflexions and exercises for practice that encourage creative thought.
2. Building up the skills of English Language Teachers: It is important for teacher educators to have chances to attend regular workshops and trainings: these should focus on effective ways to teach grammar and word structure, including how explicit instruction works in theory and practice. This will help improve the quality of teaching given to students.
3. Reviewing and Revising Curriculum: The syllabus of English language classes in Education Colleges needs to be examined, giving proper emphasis to morphology. This should mean making more room for thorough teaching of morphological rules and real use of the language.
4. Use of Supplementary Materials and Technology: Educators ought to make use of different teaching tools like interactive software, word-formation games and digital platforms that help improve morphological skills through clear or contextual learning.
5. Balanced Pedagogical Approach: While the focus should be on explicit instruction, teachers are required to use a mixed method that involves parts of implicit teaching. This helps in addressing different learning ways and supports the natural development of language skills.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that explicit instructional strategies significantly enhance the morphological competence of students in Colleges of Education. Morphology, as a critical component of English grammar, requires a deliberate and structured pedagogical approach for learners to master the rules and nuances of word formation. The superiority of explicit instruction observed in this study underscores the need to emphasize clarity, rule-based learning, and direct engagement with linguistic content in language teacher education programs.

Although implicit instruction has its advantages, especially in advancing natural acquisition and contextual usage, it is inadequate when used as the only strategy in a setting that demands grammatical precision and academic activity. Moreover, the non-significance of gender differences in performance emphasizes that both male and female learners benefit equally from sound instructional practices when provided with equal learning opportunities. Therefore, gender is not a determining factor in instructional efficacy in the area of consideration.

In essence, the research establishes that the method of instruction plays a crucial role in shaping students' linguistic competence. To improve the quality of English language education and teacher preparation in Nigeria, attention must be given to pedagogical choices that empower learners to grasp and apply linguistic knowledge effectively.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study contributes significantly to research work though its geographical scope is restricted to Colleges of Education in Osun State, Nigeria. Consequently, appropriate measures must be taken when expanding the findings to a larger population, since the results might not correctly depict the distinctness of students in all Nigerian Colleges of Education. Another limitation is on the implementation of the instructional strategies. The effectiveness of explicit, implicit and conventional strategies may be influenced by individual differences in teaching styles, interpretation of the instructional models, and the level of commitment by teachers. Such variations could affect the consistency and reliability of the treatment across research groups. Moreover, if the study was conducted over a short duration, it may not account for the long-term effects or retention of morphological knowledge by the students. Language learning, particularly morphological competence, often requires sustained exposure and practice. Thus, a limited timeframe may not capture the enduring impact of the instructional strategies. Also, the study focuses basically on morphology, which, though fundamental, is primarily an aspect of language structure. Other components which include phonology, syntax, and semantics are similarly significant in the holistic development of language proficiency. On this basis, findings from this study may not actually show the overall students' performance in the structure of English.

In conclusion, the study may not have full control over external variables such as students' prior familiarity with English, their exposure to the language outside the classroom environment, motivation levels, and socio-economic settings. These factors could greatly impact students' learning outcomes but may be difficult to separate them entirely within the study design.

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